

THE EMBODIMENT OF NATIONAL CUISINE IN NAKHCHIVAN FOLKLORE TEXTS¹

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ABSTRACT

We are not mistaken in saying that folklore is the treasury of the people. Because rich culture, ancient history, delicious and rich cuisine of the Azerbaijani people, freedom of will, wisdom, valuable words and so on are preserved in this box. Folklore is a source of increasing value and wealth. The article discusses the dishes of our national cuisine, which have a special share in this wealth. Azerbaijani cuisine has its own voice in world cuisine with its rich and tasty dictates: gas and sweets. The share of the people here is undeniable. It is noteworthy that the national dishes of Azerbaijani cuisine have been widely developed in the folklore texts of the people. Here, the position of the development of the names of dishes in the folklore texts of Azerbaijani cuisine, which is a key part of material culture, was studied, samples were selected and filtered. During the analysis, it was found that in the folklore texts of the territory of Nakhchivan there are many names of dishes related to our national cuisine, and the frequency of occurrence of these names is high. This suggests that people love national cuisine, which these dishes are prepared with soul in every home and are eaten with pleasure. Studies also show that most of the names of dishes used in the folklore materials of Nakhchivan refer to the national cuisine. In folklore texts, there are almost no dishes from the cuisine of other countries. This is due to the fact that people prefer nationality. The names of the dishes involved in the study are still widely used in our kitchens. This indicates that although the cuisine of other countries is widespread, national dishes do not lose their relevance. It is safe to say that the national dishes of Azerbaijan will continue to decorate our tables.

Keywords: national, Cuisine, folklore, Nakhchivan

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Introduction

As you know, one of the main factors acquainting the country and people with the world is its cuisine. Azerbaijani cuisine, which is a key part of material culture, occupies a special place in the world cuisine with its taste and variety. "Azerbaijani cuisine is in harmony with the culinary culture, its history, philosophy, table psychology, customs, physiology, hygiene, chemistry, technique, ethics, aesthetics, poetry and other aspects of cuisine, as well as practical skills created by the Azerbaijani people in historical harmony with environment unites in some way" [6]. So the cuisine is very important for the nation. To do this, everyone must preserve their national cuisine as a key part of their material culture and present it to the world. After all, the role of cuisine in the development of tourism is great. We know that many tourists go to other countries just for the sake of their cuisine. This gives reason to say that the kitchen is not just in the kitchen, it is important in the development of the state. Folklore samples of Nakhchivan reflect the history of the region, culture [9, 11]. Customs and traditions, life and way of life of people, their beliefs, mythical and real way of thinking. Nakhchivan is historically the most ancient and richest place of delicious salt deposits. Salt clinics, salt caves and salt stone axes were found on this land. Salt mining in the territory of Nakhchivan has its roots in the Stone Age. This is evidenced by the stone axes, tools and picks found here during archaeological excavations in 1870. Stone axes found in Duzdag (salt mountain) were sent to the museums of Nakhchivan, St. Petersburg and Tiflis [10.72].

Azerbaijani cuisine is one of the ancient and rich cuisines. Although the basis of our cuisine is our national dishes, there are many dishes from the cuisines of other countries. Of course, these last times have increased even more. One of the main reasons for this is the accessibility of the Internet, the presence of the largest search engine Google and the creation of a YouTube channel in visual or audio format. Because the ladies use them to cook dinner. However, it should be noted that no matter how much we turn to the cuisine of other countries, our own national dishes take first place on our table. Because the most delicious Azerbaijani fillings, pilaf, meatballs, bozbashi, callapach, yogurt inoculation and so on. Such gourmet dishes have an irreplaceable taste. These delicious dishes are very popular among the people and are reflected in the cultural culture created by the people. Delicious and satisfying national dishes of Azerbaijan have enriched and enriched the folklore material with their beauty. By the way, there are dishes belonging to each region of Azerbaijan, which is reflected in the folklore of each region. Let's filter some names of dishes used in Nakhchivan folklore texts:

"My wife puts the bread in the middle. The food is also meatballs. They eat bozbashi. They want meatballs, and suddenly the guest says:

-Native brother ...

He says:

-Yes bro. Wife, don't cover the meatballs, let me answer the guest's question" [1, p.106].

Meatballs, which are a delicious taste of our cuisine, are eaten in two parts in many parts of our country. First, water is cut, then the breast is crushed and eaten. We see this in the example above. Note that we cut bread into the water of a dish we call bozbash and eat it with bread. Here I recall a riddle that arose in Nakhchivan. Where do they eat lavash with lavash?

In other stories, we meet the name of the meatball dish. Although meatballs and meatballs look similar, they are different dishes. Remember, meatballs are peas in a bowl. This does not happen in meatballs. We see a paragraph about meatballs in Mullah Allahgulu's Tale:

"The servant of God came to me to tell me that my wife was hungry. Let's see what you have prepared from meat. My wife brings me, man, I cooked cutlets, come in and sit down" [4, p.158].

In this story, we meet the names of our other national dishes - dolma, bozbash:

"One of the wives said, "I made meatballs. Don't you know I don't eat meatballs?" Someone said, I hung a goat, he told me, but don't you know, I don't eat a goat, someone said, I ate a scarecrow, don't you know, I don't eat a scarecrow?" [4, p.158].

Of course, it is impossible not to eat these dishes. Here Mullah Allahgulu oppresses his wives because he is a tyrant. That's why he says, "I don't eat" what is offered to him. These dishes are popular dishes of our national cuisine.

In the same story, we see how the tyrant mullah asks for pilaf:

"Mulla Allahgulu shouted that I want pilaf. The wife said: "This is pilaf for you" [4, p.159].

Knowing the character of the mullah, his wife cooks all the food and cooks. He brings it to the table whenever he wants. This example, in fact, shows how skillful an Azerbaijani woman is, how much work she has to do, how well she knows the kitchen.

The saying about dolma is also widespread among the people.

You're tired of being full and it won't be a day.

Khashil is one of the dishes of our national cuisine. Let's see how the name of this dish is used in folklore examples:

"Hamid woke up again when he wanted to. His mother cooked the food. Maybe Hamid will help: "his mother sent a message to his father with him" [5, p.67].

Or:

"At work, the bakers baked bread and put a large bowl on a chair, let them eat" [4, p.23].

We also meet the name of this dish in the fairy tale "Two neighbours":

"One day, poor neighbors - a husband and wife - are sitting in the yard. They see the rich man's wife cooking. A man says to his wife:

- Wife, I'm hungry. But how can he eat it? [3, p.179].

Based on the examples, it can be said that the name of this dish is often used in folklore texts. The reason for this is that everyone has the strength and ability to cook it, because it is done quickly and does not require large expenses.

It is known that Nakhchivan fish is also popular among the people. Our fish cuisine is very rich, as we have a variety of fish dishes. We also find this in folklore examples:

"He buys and brings fish. She says, madam, cook and eat fish" [4, p.13].

Ashin occupies a special place among the indispensable dishes of the Azerbaijani national cuisine. This dish rich in variety (200 varieties) is reflected in world cuisine. In some regions, this dish, known as ashy plov, is called the king of our tables. And this name deserved its taste and appearance. Since he is considered the king of the tables, at the wedding, at the party of happy days, food comes at the end. And it says in the quote:

The stone flies out of the window

The king of tables eats.

It is from the masterpiece of this dish that dancers and dancers in national costumes bring vaccinations for engagements and weddings. This confirms the nationality of the dish, its value, in a word, its "royal" position. Let's see where the name of this dish is often found in folklore texts:

In the evening I prepared a vaccine,

I put poppies on top

He is the daughter-in-law's secret

Welcome, welcome [4, p.102].

The name Ash is also found in kisses:

Afruz, Afruz, crucian carp,

When the pot boils.

Afruz goes to work

When the bear crosses the mountain [3, p.96].

In the proverb we find it like pilaf:

Laughter is ridiculous; plov is a lynx [3, p.116].

In the above example, the language of Mullah Allahgulu expresses the name of eating pilaf.

Since pilaf or soup is a personal meal, on all special days it is always on the table. On festive evenings, on past Wednesdays, for engagements, weddings, etc. In other good deeds, such as plov, there is table decoration. Keep in mind that not everyone can cook *ash* well.

I remember a saying about this:

The rain made the pilaf delicious,

The bride's face turned pale.

Or what we sometimes use as a joke:

What is this pilaf, where is its oil?

Such expressions are widespread among the people.

There are also many dishes made with eggs. This varied food is eaten mainly in the morning and at lunchtime. Because they say eggs are hard to digest, so they don't eat eggs before bed. This quick-

cooking dish is on the menu of almost every home. We see the name of this dish in the joke "I ate at home." Reading from this anecdote:

"Uncle Ai, why don't you cut off a piece of our bread?"

He laughs at the butcher and says:

"Sister, don't worry, I knew that you were cooking eggs, so I came home to eat eggs" [4, p.382].

It is also used in proverbs:

Meat is life, eggs are half.

Sometimes people with monkeys are told: "Today he eats protein, and leaves the yolk for tomorrow."

We mentioned above that pilaf is also called ash. However, the soup is also processed into other dishes. For example: porridge, yogurt, milk, etc. We read from the joke "Stone on the horse, eat from above":

"In the morning they boil milk. It attracts ticks. He sees that he puts more on his mother than on his hips" [4, p.397].

Soup made in the name of laughter means the name of milk soup. In the example below, we are confronted with the name of the yogurt vaccine eaten:

"A woman cooks a piece of kefir from a thousand oppressions. When the time comes, he will eat the pot and eat it at the street door" [2, p.33].

Shish kebab varieties are also masterpieces of our national cuisine. Men are the main chefs of this dish, which has a wide range. And this dish can be called mainly a field dish. Since not every home has facilities for cooking, this food is mostly cooked or ordered on the street - in the chimney. Those who live in yard houses slaughter sheep and make kebabs when their dear guests come. Friends often cut lamb and make kebabs when they get together. Men cutting and preparing shish kebabs are also reflected in folklore texts. If the people do this, then it will be reflected in their own folklore texts. Consider this example:

"The shepherd takes the dog and follows the flock. When it arrives, the harams gather the herd together, slaughter the male and cook barbecue" [2, p.91].

Kebab, a special dish of the winter months, is loved and eaten for its vitamins and strength. This dish takes time and effort to prepare. Therefore, not everyone can cook this dish. The ladies who cook also have a great ahsan. As the folklore text says:

"The Shah came to visit his sister. The girl boiled the skull in the pond. The Shah was stunned to see his sister in armor" [3, p.191].

The fact that Shah was taken aback by the way his sister cooks here indicates that this dish was a little difficult to prepare.

Or:

On the one hand, as soon as our daughter cooked a barbecue on a spit, she took some meat and water from a saucer and carried it to her mother with the words: *"I brought a share to my father" [2, p.156].*

I remember a recent popular saying about the skull.

The meat of fish skulls, they are eaten with the hands

Chicken occupies a special place in our cuisine among dishes distinguished by originality and taste. People eat it more as fried and squeaky. When you go on a trip, it is most often cooked in the form of a roast and put in a travel bag. We meet the idea in the tale of the golden rooster:

"Three brothers are preparing to leave. Everyone takes a bag of gold. Alemdar's mother cooks three chickens for him. The brothers are leaving" [2, p.222].

There are also many dishes made from goose meat. Admittedly, goose meat, like other products, is not eaten and loved by everyone. In the folklore texts we also follow the point about the goose meat dish:

"Take this gas and prepare it. When it is ready, I will send a man and you will give him food" [2, p.241].

Although not everyone eats goose, they say that it is very tasty. The saying "You haven't eaten goose, you don't know its taste" is not accidental. Most likely, this phrase was invented by those who love and eat goose meat.

In the legends about Ashug, we also meet the names of a number of delicious dishes. For example:

"They used to cook food in the tandoor. They would cut khangal, boil dry land, cook kaledzham" [2, p.470].

In this example, along with our national dishes, we also meet the cuisine of other countries. Although the dishes prepared here are national, khangal is one of the dishes of Georgian cuisine.

We also meet the names of food in folk customs:

"Seven days before the harvest, they say: "Respect the harvest," and they make halva, cook seasonal food and distribute it to homes so that there is plenty of bread" [3, p.25].

Please note that some of the food can be distributed to homes. In this example, chapters, hadiths, verses, verses, etc. dishes can be shown as. The name of the torture we mentioned is different in our dialects and dialects - jigatai, tangov, hot water, etc. are widely used by name. The cooking time of this dish falls mainly in October-November. Because everyone cooks a roast for the winter. Then comes torture food.

Flour products also occupy a special place in our kitchen. Shekerbura, baklava, bread, thick, sugar bread, etc. can specify the name. Many of these names are also used in Nakhchivan folklore texts. For example:

"The vizier went to the city. It's been a long time. He returned with a loaf of bread and food" [2, p.235].

"You slaughter some sheep and eat their meat, spin wool on your face, weave warm clothes, put on a skin, bake bread from ear flour, and go out in the spring" [2, p.57].

"His mother cooks thicker and goes to the snow" [4, p.181].

We are also seeing the evolution of food names in games. For example:

Muhammad's grandmother

Bread baked in sugar.

At this length

Brevity at this height [4, p.627].

The assortment of bread in our kitchen is very rich. We met several kinds of this in folklore genres.

Conclusion

In the course of the analysis, we found very few names of dishes in folklore texts related to the cuisine of other countries. This is also pleasing. It is commendable to see and observe our national cuisine in folklore texts that reflect our ancient culture and spiritual values. It seems that the food of other countries, which influences our daily cuisine, could not but influence our folklore. The more conservative our people are in protecting their material culture, the more conservative they are in carrying out the mission of preserving and transmitting our spiritual culture to the future.

References:

1. Azerbaijani fairy tales. (2005). Nakhchivan. I vol. Baku, 296 p.
2. Nakhchivan folklore anthology. (2010). I vol. Nakhchivan: Ajami, 512 p.
3. Nakhchivan folklore anthology. (2011). Volume 2. Nakhchivan: Ajami, 496 p.
4. Anthology of folklore of Nakhchivan. (2012). Volume III. Nakhchivan: Ajami, 560 p.
5. Saadat Hajiyeva. (2017). My mint world. Baku. 245 p.
6. <https://azerbaijan.az/related-information/55132>
7. Janet Afary & Kamran Afary (2021) Mollā Nasreddin and the creative Cauldron of Transcaucasia, *British Journal of Middle Eastern Studies*, 48:4, 563-595, DOI: 10.1080/13530194.2019.1659130
8. Zaur Gasimov (2021) Observing Iran from Baku: Iranian Studies in Soviet and Post-Soviet Azerbaijan, *Iranian Studies*, DOI: 10.1080/00210862.2020.1865136
9. Galib Bashirov (2018) Islamic discourses in Azerbaijan: the securitization of 'non-traditional religious movements', *Central Asian Survey*, 37:1, 31-49, DOI: 10.1080/02634937.2017.1418735
10. Tadeusz Swietochowski (1991) The politics of a literary language and the rise of national identity in Russian Azerbaijan before 1920, *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 14:1, 55-63, DOI: 10.1080/01419870.1991.9993698